

HOW DO OGD INITIATIVES AFFECT TRANSPARENCY? A POST-ANALYSIS ON DEVELOPED INDICES

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Open Government Data (OGD) refers to the datasets pertaining to the structural, functional and operational dimensions of government bodies and are available freely (in most cases) via dedicated web portals in machine-processable formats with government-mandated open license. OGD is available across multifarious domains like climate, energy, education, transport, finance, and a humungous set of sectors where the government operates (Janssen, 2011). As an advanced stage of e-government (electronic government) where the impetus is on citizen collaboration and participation in administration, OGD initiatives seek to refurbish public service delivery with this novel administrative innovation (Vetro et al., 2016). The launch of OGD initiatives by the governments around the globe is a phenomenal action in several countries. OGD is re-used by diverse set of stakeholders (academia, professionals, businesses, non-governmental organizations, and the like) for value creation and innovation. OGD is also known to bring about economic growth (Attard et al., 2015). Nonetheless, one of the main goals of any OGD initiative is to improve transparency of and trust on governmental operations and decisions (Gonzalvez-Gallego et al., 2020).

Extant literature on OGD has advanced a number of conceptual frameworks to further our understanding of the domain. Various studies have investigated the users' intention to use, adopt and acknowledge the utilitarian facet of OGD in terms of product and/or service improvisation (Dawes et al., 2016; Sieber and Johnson, 2015; Srimuang et al., 2017). Fewer concentrate on the transparency factors influenced by OGD or vice versa (Abu Shanab, 2015a; Abu-Shanab, 2015b; Jetzek et al., 2013; Lee and Kwak, 2011; Sandoval-Almazan and Gil-Garcia, 2016; Wirtz and Birkmeyer, 2015). The latter ones argue that there is a connection between the impact of GDP or GDP growth rate with the implementation of OGD initiatives and, ipso facto, with the rate of participation and trust. But most of the above studies are either qualitative or conceptual based on experts' opinions. Thus, they are not based on absolute quantitative metrics and indices. This study tries to fill in this gap by investigating the correlation and the degree of influence of open data on transparency, GDP and trust using well-established indicators. Thus, the present study addresses the call made by Charalabidis and his colleagues that OGD research is required to appreciate the

“use of OGD as part of anticorruption programs in order to increase public sector accountability and credibility” (Charalabidis et al., 2016).

Across the globe, countries have been taking steps to curb corruption and bring about transparency in their functioning. Furthermore, governments are resorting to bolster trust among the citizens regarding the efficacy of the government functioning. Connecting the dots with the foregoing, countries which have spearheaded the OGD initiatives already are also stepping up their drives towards ensuring that their OGD portals are as much “open” as possible, wherein openness is defined in terms of transparency, completeness, accuracy, timeliness, and other key criteria. Capturing these aforesaid dimensions in the present study along with the dimension of economic growth of the countries is the key contribution of the present study. Specifically, whereas, there has been an impetus on countries’ aiming to improve their performance across the transparency rankings (Corruption Perception Index as per the Transparency International rankings or the World Press Freedom Index (WPFI) as per the Reporters Without Frontiers) and the GDP (Gross Domestic Product) indices, concomitantly, governments have been vying top-notch rankings on the ODIN (Open Data Inventory that measures the degree of openness of the OGD portals) indicator as well. Furthermore, governments are striving to forge ties with the citizens to bolster the trust of the latter in them (GovData360).

Corruption Perception Index (CPI)-released by Transparency International- is a widely-acclaimed indicator against which countries are ranked on the basis of the perceptions regarding corruption as far as the public sector is concerned (Transparency International, 2022). CPI assesses dimensions such as bribery, diversion of public funds, public officials' making private gains, red-tapism, nepotism, etc. World Press Freedom Index (WPFI) is annually released by the Reporters Without Frontiers wherein the freedom of information and communication is gauged (RSF, 2022). The Gross Domestic Product (GDP) helps to assess the "health" of a country's economy such that the value of all the goods and services produced over a particular time period is specified-this is also referred to as the size of the economy (Talukdar, 2013). Trust in government may be captured by the indices referred to in the indices like citizens' participatory competence, civil rights, constitutional discretion, etc.(GovData360, 2022). Open Data Inventory (ODIN) evaluates the extent to which the open data provided via the online portal are "open" and "complete" on the bases of machine readability (allow users to easily process data using a computer, e.g. XLS, XLSX, CSV, Stata, SAS, SPSS, JSON, CDF, RDF, XML, and TXT files), non-proprietary format (allow users to access data without requiring the use of a costly, proprietary software, e.g. PDF, HTML, XLSX, DOCX, CSV, JSON, XML, and TXT files), download options (bulk download, API, and user-select options), metadata availability (including definition of the indicator, date of upload to website or when dataset was last updated and name of data source) and terms of use (with "open" terms of use or open data license) (ODIN, 2022).

The purport of the study is to situate a country’s OGD initiative across four axes-CPI, WPFI, GDP and GovData360 rankings vis-a-vis ODIN. There are three reasons for selecting these 4 metrics: first, OGD initiative is an attempt to bolster transparency and the same gets reflected in the CPI which measures the extent of corruption whilst WPFI captures the freedom of speech and expression, and hence transparency; second, GDP a country’s GDP indicates its economic well-being and to launch and institutionalize an OGD initiative, a country’s GDP should be factored into; and, finally, ODIN assesses the extent to which the datasets available on the country’s OGD

portal meet the internationally-acknowledged “openness” metrics, and, hence reflective of the quality of the datasets which, in turn, is symbolic of the extent of progressive and advanced state of an OGD initiative. In line with these dimensions, a country’s OGD initiative is explained using a conceptual framework. Whereas studies abound regarding the conceptual frameworks linked with OGD, an understanding of the countries’ status vis-a-vis the parameters chosen in this study merits consideration-the present study seeks to plug the gap.

That there is a linkage between corruption (as measured by CPI and WPI) and economic development (as measured by GDP) has been attested (Tanzi and Davoodi, 1998; Ibraheem et al., 2013; Lucic et al., 2016; Grundler and Potrafke, 2019). Likewise, extant research on OGD shows that OGD initiatives and GDP are related with each other (Magalhaes et al., 2013; Saxena, 2017; Leviakangas and Molarius, 2020; Zeleti et al., 2016; Gonzalez-Zapata and Heeks, 2015) -however, empirical investigation on this linkage has remained few and far between. Finally, there has been scant research to study the linkage between the ODIN rankings and transparency (which is linked with trust and, inter alia, corruption) (See Gonzalez-Gallego and Nieto-Torrejon, 2021). Therefore, it is justified to appreciate the manner in which the three dimensions are inter-linked in terms of the OGD initiatives of the governments. Specifically, we will plot the countries in the quadrants (Table 1).

Table 1. Quadrant framework to understand the OGD initiative across Transparency ranking-GDP axes-ODIN scores (Source: Authors).

	GDP (High)	GDP (Low)
Transparency ranking/ODIN score (High)	Established OGD initiative (Eg: The Netherlands)	Work-in-progress OGD initiative (Eg: Greece; Spain)
Transparency ranking/ODIN score (Low)	Crawling OGD initiative (Eg: India)	Shelve-it-off OGD initiative (Eg: Bhutan)

Backed by data on 28 countries, the present study seeks to present a quadrant analysis validated with an empirical framework wherein the correlations between the transparency, trust and GDP rankings shall be studied with the lens of the ODIN rankings. These correlation-based deductions shall be followed up by a regression analysis wherein the ODIN serves as the dependent variable and the GDP figures, Trust indices and CPI indices shall figure as independent variables. Findings from the data analyses pitch, for instance, The Netherlands in the “Established”, Greece in the “Work-in-progress”, India in the “Crawling” and Sri Lanka in the “Shelve-it-off” quadrants. Likewise, other countries have been mapped across the axes to drive home the linkage between the indices.

This study makes a significant contribution towards furthering our understanding of the OGD phenomenon regarding its correlation with transparency, trust and GDP. The results indicate strong correlations among all these factors providing a robust empirical validation on the existing theoretical and conceptual background. Moreover, the study presents the developed clusters of OGD initiatives and discusses them regarding the Open Data Maturity Index. Future research pointers and practitioner implications constitute the concluding segments of the study.

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